

Motion- and field-robust ultra-high-resolution whole-brain imaging enabled by servo navigation

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Synopsis

Motivation

Even subtle involuntary motion can degrade image quality in ultra-high-resolution imaging due to long acquisition times.

Goal

To reduce motion and dynamic field induced artifacts in ultra-high-resolution T_2^* -weighted imaging (0.25 mm^3) using servo navigators for prospective correction at 7T.

Approach

Servo navigators were integrated into a segmented 3D-EPI sequence to correct motion and field variations. Involuntary motion experiments were conducted, and minimum intensity projections were used to assess the effect of prospective correction on fine details in brain anatomy.

Results

Servo navigators can provide motion and field estimates with sufficiently high precision and successfully mitigate artifacts in ultra-high-resolution MRI, enabling the investigation of submillimeter brain structures.

Impact

Improvements in visibility of small vessels demonstrate the capability of servo navigators to correct for small motions and field changes during ultra-high-resolution T2*-weighted whole-brain imaging (0.25mm isotropic) using 3D-EPI.

Introduction

Image quality in ultra-high-resolution is susceptible to artifacts due to involuntary small motions, which are inevitable for prolonged acquisition times. In previous studies, interleaved multi-shot 3D-EPI demonstrated to be effective for fast T2*-weighted imaging, significantly decreasing scan times compared to conventional 3D-GRE[1,2]. Still, averaging of multiple highly-accelerated scans is needed at high resolutions to keep intra-volume motion in the individual averages acceptable. Furthermore, gradient heating in EPI is notorious for causing field drifts, which can affect image quality and degrade accuracy of MR-based navigation approaches. Servo navigators demonstrated to be capable of measuring motion and dynamic field changes with high precision[3,4]. In this work, we present an application of servo navigators for single-average, ultra-high-resolution 3D-EPI imaging.

Methods

Servo navigators[3] (k-space radius=400 rad/m, TA=2.3 ms) were integrated into a segmented 3D-EPI[5] (0.25 mm isotropic whole-brain protocol) following each RF excitation. The linear perturbation model included rigid body motion parameters and B0 coefficients (up to first-order spherical harmonics), calibrated with additional navigators under 5 μ T/m gradient offsets (finite-difference method[4]). Prospective motion correction (PMC) was performed per shot with minimal latency of one shot-TR by libXPACE[6]. The field was adjusted after each motion update and the servo control[3,4] maintained the linear model range. Due to the short sequence timing and due to fast and strong EPI gradient switching, eddy currents induced in the preceding shot-TR were present during the subsequent orbital navigator (Onav) readout. These eddy currents varied with preceding echo time shifting[7] and phase encoding gradient amplitudes. This systematic pattern per shot in the predicted time series was estimated during the first 4 segments and recalculated during run-time (same window size) due to gradual changes induced by the second phase encoding gradients. Additionally, a moving average filter (window size=15 shots) was employed to increase parameter precision. Two healthy subjects were scanned using a MAGNETOM 7T Plus scanner (Siemens Healthineers, Erlangen, Germany) equipped with a 32 channel Rx (8Tx) head coil (Nova Medical Inc, Wilmington, Delaware, USA). The subjects were instructed to remain still. In the first subject experiment, only PMC was applied (PMC0, with frequency offset correction only applied to the Onav), while the second was conducted with additional dynamic shimming up to first order (PMC1). Each scan was repeated without PMC, in which Onav data were recorded without servo control. The two human experiments followed slightly different protocols (Table 1). To identify changes in small structures, minimum-intensity projections (mIPs) of all magnitude images

were calculated (10mm slab) and matched as accurately as possible without registering the images, thereby avoiding interpolation bias.

Experiment	1	2
Investigated model	PMC0	PMC1
Iso. resolution [mm]	0.25	0.25
TA [min:s]	11:16	19:26
Shot-TR [ms]	40	50
TE [ms]	21	23
EPI factor	10	11
Echo spacing [ms]	2.97	2.78
CAIPI Parallel imaging	3 x 1y1	2 x 1y1
RF pulse	Spatially non-selective Water-excitation (12°)	Slab-selective (15°) + fat saturation (85°)
Readout bandwidth [Hz/ Pixel]	402	432
FOV [mm]	194 (H>F) x 209.52 (A>P)	145 (L>R) x 208.95 (A>P)
Slices	594 (L>R)	606 (H>F)

Table 1: Protocol parameters for the two experiments without (PMC0) and with additional dynamic shimming (PMC1).

Results

In Fig. 1, mIPs of the PMC0 experiment are compared. While the motion trajectories show high similarity, blurring in the frontal lobe can be observed in the uncorrected image. This blurring is reduced with PMC, although not entirely, enhancing the visibility of small vessels. Additionally, more details of small structures can be identified in the second zoom.

The results of the PMC1 experiment are illustrated in Figures 2 and 3. Drifts are observed in the frequency offset (~ 1 Hz/min) and z-shim correction (~ 0.1 μ T/min). Compared to no correction, the overall image quality is improved, and the visibility of small vessels is enhanced with PMC1. Small vessels close to the CSF (Fig. 2) exhibit sharper edges and improved localization compared to their broadened appearance without any corrections. In a lower slice (Fig. 3), blurring artifacts can be observed in the frontal lobe, while the tissue edge appears sharper with PMC1. Furthermore, small vessels that spread from the CSF are more defined and appear longer due to reduced motion blur in the raw magnitude images prior to minimum-intensity projection. The effectiveness of the eddy current correction is demonstrated in Figure 4. Without any correction, the precision is significantly reduced.

Fig.1 - mIPs of the PMC0 experiment. Without PMC, small vessels in the frontal lobe are obscured due to blurring artifacts. With PMC applied, blurring is significantly reduced, allowing these vessels to be seen in high detail. The motion trajectories (or FOV updates) exhibit high similarity, while the frequency offset f_0 (only used for demodulation of the navigator) shows a large drift of 2 Hz/min.

Fig.2 - mIPs of the PMC1 experiment. Motion estimates reveal increased rotation around the left-right axis (R_z) during acquisition of the corrected image. Nevertheless, overall image quality is clearly improved, particularly for small vessels near the CSF, which become more defined. The stabilized phase offset ϕ in the PMC1 case indicates that the

frequency was successfully updated in real-time.

Fig.3 - Lower slice of the PMC1 experiment. Blurring artifacts in the frontal lobe are reduced and small vessels extending from the CSF become visible.

Fig. 4 - Motion and field parameters before and after eddy current correction (PMC1). Without corrections, the parameters display low precision. In the lower section, the initial phase of the measurement is presented: 4 segments are acquired to determine the systematic pattern before applying significant updates. After ~ 15 s, eddy-current-induced biases are removed, and FOV updates are sent with significantly increased precision. The filter adds a small delay, particularly noticeable in the rigid body parameters. The Onav reveals sensitivity to physiological motion.

Discussion and Conclusion

The PMC0 experiment shows large improvements in the visibility of small structures in the mIPs due to PMC. The improvements observed in the PMC1 experiment also allowed the detection of small vessels. The effect of dynamic shimming is difficult to separate from PMC. However, the image quality was not adversely affected by dynamic shimming despite the long TE. It is important to note that at such long echo times, applying field offsets and dynamic shimming is difficult, especially in this 3D-EPI sequence, where strong eddy current variations occur during the navigator readout. Image quality could be further improved by optimizing the filter; exploring different window sizes for motion correction and field drift compensation may help maximizing sensitivity to fast motion while maintaining optimal sensitivity to the slower field drifts.

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